

Proposal: Community Cluster (CC)

NFDI4OBJECTS

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

RDM-Support

Chairs: Sandra Schröder-Spang (Hochschule Mainz); Nina Hohm (Goethe-Universität Frankfurt)

NFDI4Objects-Bodies Involved: Task Area 6, Task Area 7

External Connection: DALIA; EduTrain, insb. AP7: Networking and Outreach as well as Working Group RDM-Helpdesk-Network; State Initiatives Research Data Management (bwFDM, FDM-BB, HeFDI, fdm.nrw, fdm.rlp, SaxFDM, TKFDM, fdm-bayern.org, UBRA, FDM-NDS, FDM-SH); Data Competence Centers (Hermes, SODA, WiNoDa); Helpdesks of NFDI4Memory, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Earth, FAIRagro and Text+

Short Name of the Mailing List: n4o_cc_fdmsupport

Steering Committee Resolution: 24.10.2025

Topics and Objectives

The Community Cluster “RDM Support” serves as a contact and exchange platform for the NFDI4Objects consortium with experienced practitioners in the field of RDM consulting. These experts work at universities, research institutions, government agencies, companies, and RDM associations, as well as in the RDM Helpdesk Network working group of the NFDI Training & Education division. The Community Cluster is intended to ensure that RDM consultants have access to up-to-date information on results and services from the consortium for the NFDI4Objects community in their home institutions. Consulting practice highlights the needs of the NFDI4Objects community. Through systematic and documented information exchange within the Community Cluster, the experts can pass on these needs to the consortium. The focus is therefore on questions such as “What’s new at NFDI4Objects?” or “What community needs were identified during the consultation?”. Community Cluster meetings are scheduled two to four times a year (virtually). Task area 6 will prepare, support, and document these meetings. Contents of the Community Cluster RDM consultation will be forwarded to the EduTrain division of NFDI e.V.

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Out of Scope

Community Cluster RDM Consulting focuses on the RDM needs of the NFDI4Objects community. General topics related to RDM and training should only be discussed if they result in immediate action requirements for NFDI4Objects. The focus lies on the practice and consulting for the NFDI4Objects community. The Community Cluster does not serve as an RDM helpdesk but as an exchange platform for RDM consultants. Neither is it a supplement to the EduTrain section of the NFDI e.V. or existing regional networks. No Temporary Working Groups are currently planned. However, if specific papers are to be produced, this option can be used at any time.

Intended Work Results

Currently, no Temporary Working Groups are planned. However, the Community Cluster can make use of this option at any time if specific papers need to be produced.